

THE USE OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IS THE MAIN BASIS OF HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry" No.3532, also PD-5707 dated April 10, 2019 "On measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2019-2021" and "On measures for the protection, cultural cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of medicinal plants growing in the wild" "As stated in the decisions of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-4670 dated April 10, 2020, the ways of finding cures for various diseases for mankind have been studied using medicinal plants, a wide path has been opened for human health, and they are serving in practical use in medicine. The article examines the rational use of medicinal plants and the fact that they are the basis of human health.

Keywords: medicinal plants, cranberries, salvia, valerian, allspice, Turkestan ayuga, liverwort, bur-marigold, bush system, cumin.

Introduction. Based on the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 14, 2018 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry" No. PD-3532, in order to protect human health, mankind has been using various medicines for thousands of years and the search for medicines for pain. Uzbekistan occupies a unique historical place and authority among the countries of the world in the use of medicinal plants. In particular, our ancestors knew the properties of medicinal plants and knew how to use them effectively. Our great scientist, well known in history from the beginning, Abu Ali Ibn Sina of the 11th century, studied the effect of using medicinal plants from a practical aspect in medicine based on various experiences. The results of the great and world-wide important research work of the scientist are recognized by scientists all over the world, and even today, even after centuries, the unique information in his works is of great importance for mankind in the prevention of various diseases.

Geographically, Uzbekistan is rich in the diversity of medicinal plants. About 4,500 types of medicinal plants can be found here naturally. Among them, about 1200 types of medicinal plants have medicinal properties, and based on the Law and decrees, it was determined that they are part of the wealth of the plant world of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the data of the World Health Organization, 60% of the available medicines are preparations obtained from raw materials of medicinal plants. Currently, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 112 types of medicinal plants are officially allowed to be used in medicine, and 80% of these medicinal plants are naturally growing plants.

In addition, on April 10, 2020, Resolution PD-4670 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to protect medicinal plants growing in the wild, cultivated, processing and rational use of available resources" The goal is to create an additional value chain, integrating education, science and production processes. After all, it is necessary to integrate education, science and production, continuously supply the pharmaceutical industry with raw materials of

medicinal plants that meet international requirements, reduce the volume of imports, increase the volume of exports by breeding the species in high demand in foreign countries by plantation method, preserve and expand the area of medicinal plants in the wild. Today it is considered one of the urgent and important issues.

Today, the demand for natural medicines in the countries of the world is increasing by 6-7% per year, and according to the forecast of international experts, in 2022 the annual turnover will exceed 35 billion dollars. Countries such as China, India, Canada, and the United States have extensive experience in the conservation of medicinal and spice plants growing in the wild, and in the cultivation of cultivated plantations. Currently, based on the decisions and decrees of our state, a cluster system is widely organized and great works are being carried out.

In Uzbekistan, 112 of the 1,200 types of medicinal plants are used in the pharmaceutical industry. In this direction, in order to effectively use the existing opportunities in the republic, specific measures are being taken to systematically introduce the cultivation of medicinal and spice plants in the wild and cultured way, to increase the volume of production, processing and export.

In 2018, medicinal plants were grown on 54,600 hectares of land owned by farms, other organizations and enterprises across the country and were sent to the domestic and foreign markets. It is planned to increase medicinal plant plantations to 103,700 hectares during 2020-2023. However, unfortunately, the level of use of natural medicinal plants does not meet the demand. The raw material reserve of naturally growing plants is limited, and one of the urgent problems is to preserve them, study their bioecological properties, properly use the raw material reserve, and develop scientifically based methods of reproduction.

In Uzbekistan, we can see that measures to supply the needs of the pharmaceutical industry with raw materials of medicinal plants, to enrich the local flora with new introduced plant species, and to develop technologies for their cultivation have developed dramatically. In our country, special farms for growing medicinal plants have been established in Jizzakh, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Surkhandarya and Tashkent regions. We know from scientific studies that medicinal properties of medicinal plants are not the same everywhere. The preservation of the medicinal properties of the plants is directly related to the composition of the terrain and the natural climatic conditions. Medicinal plants: medicinal plants such as Tajik cowra, licorice, Turkestan ayuga, liverwort, bur-marigold are of great importance for human health. Creating their reserves is one of the most urgent issues. Currently, the implementation of the practice of specialization of districts for the cultivation of more than 50 types of medicinal plants is given special attention in the above-mentioned decision PQ-4670 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and great work is being done to protect human health. Uzun, Boysun, Kyzirik districts are specialized in Tajik cowberry, in Yakkabog, Kitab districts of Kashkadarya region, valerian and salvia, in Pop, Chust, Torakorgan districts of Namangan region, valerian is also grown, and in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Syrdarya, and Khorezm regions, great efforts are being made to restore human health.

At the current time, when viral-infectious diseases are on the rise all over the world, the demand for natural medicines made from plant raw materials, which are harmless to the human body and increase human immunity, is increasing day by day. Therefore, the use of medicinal plants is one of the most important tasks. Most importantly, the cultivation of medicinal plants is considered a good source of income. For example: the cruciferous plant is necessary for human health, it belongs to the cruciferous family, there are more than 170 species of it on earth, and 50

species are found in our country. 10 types of sassik blankets are used to obtain resin-glue. In nature, sassy carpet is widely distributed, and glue-resin is mainly obtained from this species.

Kovrak grows mainly on sandy deserts, hills, mountain slopes and foothills, on clean soil. It has long been used in folk medicine for the treatment of dangerous swellings and wounds, and the alcohol tincture of glue-tar obtained from it has been used for asthma, vascular spasms and nervous diseases. In medicine, carpet glue-resin - *assa-foetida* is used as a powder, emulsion and alcohol tincture, as well as an anti-inflammatory and sedative agent. In Iran, Pakistan, India, and Afghanistan, its glue and roots are used as a spice in cooking, in the cosmetics industry, and in the production of perfumes. Cowrak plant is considered an incomparable medicinal plant for the treatment of varicose veins, pulmonary tuberculosis, ringworm, wounds, whooping cough, toothache, nerves and other diseases, gives strength to a person, expels phlegm and drives away worms.

The implementation of the following actions is of great importance:

1. Establishment of special plantations for the growth of medicinal plants in remote areas;
2. With the introduction of intensive technologies of cultivation of medicinal plants and the rational use of natural growth areas, gradually increasing the volume of their cultivation;
3. Establishment of plantations of medicinal plants, deep processing of medicinal plants on an industrial basis, and production of exportable products with high added value;
4. Effective organization of cooperation of business entities with state management bodies, local government bodies of all levels;
5. Participation in the development of projects of normative and legal documents related to the development of the field of cultivation and processing of medicinal plants, as well as implementation of environmental control of the public;
6. Coordinating the implementation of investment programs and projects in the field of cultivation and processing of medicinal plants.

REFERENCES

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5707 of April 10, 2019 "On measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry of the republic in 2019-2021".
2. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-3532 of February 14, 2018 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the pharmaceutical industry".
3. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-4670 dated April 10, 2020 of the "On measures for the protection, cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of medicinal plants growing in the wild".
4. Tokhtaev B.Yo., Makhkamov Y.Kh. and others. Organization of plantations of medicinal and edible plants and preparation of raw materials - (handbook), -Tashkent, 2015.